

Fracture Mechanics of Placental Release and Abruptio

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Abstract

Natural physiological release of the placenta from the uterus is a feature of normal childbirth. However, forced placental abruptio as a consequence of trauma often leads to maternal and fetal injury. Both release and abruptio have been viewed traditionally from strength of materials stress and strain perspectives, although both are fracture phenomena leading to delamination of the uterine-placental interface. Here, fracture mechanics formulations are developed and applied to describe placental release and abruptio. The formulations, the first of their kind, are based on the relative mechanical and surface energies of the fracture systems involved as interfacial cracks extend. In natural release, fracture is driven by uterine contraction. In forced abruptio, fracture is driven by uterine extension. In both cases, the fracture resistance of the interface increases with crack advance. Prior experimental observations are adapted to the fracture mechanics models and predicted behavior is consistent with release and abruptio observations. The models provide a firm foundation for more effective treatment and prevention of hemorrhage and other injuries that can occur in childbirth and as a consequence of maternal trauma.

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1 Introduction

Maternal and fetal well-being during female pregnancy and childbirth are significant personal and public health issues, with many social, economic, and physiological aspects. A major factor in maintaining such well-being during pregnancy is proper functioning of the interaction between maternal and fetal blood circulations, enabling supply of oxygen and nutrients and removal of deoxygenated blood and waste, to and from the fetus, respectively. An important physical component of this interaction is the *placenta*, an organ that is generated on pregnancy, functions throughout pregnancy, and is then expelled following childbirth [1–4]. The placenta is attached to the interior of the maternal uterus on one face and the fetal umbilical cord on the other, Fig 1. The uterine-placental interface (UPI) is thus a critical factor in maternal and fetal health, as noted in many recent surveys and reviews: If the UPI does not form correctly during gestation, the fetus does not then receive adequate oxygen and nutrients, leading to many of the “Great Obstetrical Syndromes” of pregnancy [5]. If during gestation the UPI is delaminated by trauma or external forces, often occurring during motor vehicle crashes, oxygen and nutrient flow are also disrupted [6, 7]. The phenomenon of UPI delamination or separation is known as placental abruption or “abruptio placentae” [8,9]. If the UPI does not release correctly during natural childbirth maternal hemorrhage can occur [10,11]. In the latter two cases, fetal and maternal demise are common. Placental abruption is the leading cause of fetal mortality in motor vehicle crashes [12]; fetal mortality significantly outnumbers maternal mortality in such crashes [13, 14]. Hemorrhage after childbirth is the leading cause of maternal mortality worldwide [10,15].

In addition to addressing these issues through clinical and epidemiological studies such as the above, there is considerable scope for additional pregnancy research based on advanced engineering approaches [16–18]. In particular, engineering perspectives on chemical transport and mechanical response are clearly applicable to understanding and describing placental and UPI behavior, and thus have great potential to improve maternal and fetal health. These perspectives have been used in development of techniques to study chemical transport in the placenta and UPI, using three dimensional (3-D) computational models *in silico* [19,20] and microfluidic experimental models *in vitro* [21, 22]. Engineering methodologies have also been used to study mechanical deformation of the uterus, placenta, and UPI using 3-D finite element analysis (FEA)-based computational models of motor vehicle crashes *in silico*, often with considerable complexity [23–25]. There has, however, been no attempt to study UPI failure in its fundamental nature as a fracture and delamination phenomenon. In particular, although stress and strain are well modeled in the FEA models, UPI failure behavior is controlled by *energy* transformation on fracture, reflecting integrated stress-strain behavior.

In order to improve maternal and fetal health the work here develops fundamental energy-based analyses for description and prediction of UPI fracture. The analyses are applied to forced placental abruption during trauma and natural placental release during childbirth. The work is divided into a further five sections. The next section provides overviews of the major physiological elements of human female pregnancy, the mechanics of placental abruption and release, and the mechanical properties of pregnancy related tissues. Such tissues exhibit near-linear stress-strain responses and brittle failure at moderate failure strains. An appropriate analytical approach is thus perturbation of a fracture model based on linear deformation. The next section develops the fracture mechanics of placental abruption based on this approach. The analysis provides clear physical insight into the energy changes associated with abruption and enables correspondence with the prior FEA analyses. The importance of UPI fracture resistance on abruption behavior is made clear. The crack driving force and fracture resistance are based on the experimental observations of placental and UPI behavior. The next section develops the fracture mechanics of placental release using the same mechanical properties and fracture resistance as the abruption analysis, thus enabling an internal consistency

check by comparison with separate observations. The mechanics descriptions of UPI fracture resistance and placental release are given in less detail than that for abruption. These phenomenon are considered in terms of prior fracture mechanics results that are modified to accommodate the UPI and release geometries. The next section considers perturbation of the fracture analysis by non-linear deformation characteristics of the placental material. Such perturbation leads to multiplicative scaling of the crack driving force. Finally, the discussion considers the new fracture analyses in the context of engineering approaches to improving maternal and fetal health, including suggestions for improvements to the analytical model, additions to FEA-based analyses, and applications of advanced medical devices.

2 Physiology and Mechanics Background

The placenta is a transient, multi-functional organ formed during mammalian pregnancy and expelled at birth [1–4]. During pregnancy the placenta enables a chemical exchange of oxygen, nutrients, and waste between maternal and fetal blood, connected on one side to maternal arteries and on the other side to fetal capillaries. Physically, in humans, the placenta is a spongy disc-like object, about 220 mm in diameter, 40 mm thick at the center and 10 mm thick at the edges [3,26], attached to the interior of the maternal uterus on one face and the fetal umbilical cord on the other, Fig 1. The UPI is characterized by maternal spiral arteries that penetrate the UPI and terminate in the placenta, providing oxygenated and nutriated blood. The fetal face of the placenta is heavily vascularized by arteries, veins, and capillaries that emanate from the umbilical cord and terminate in a villous, trunk + tree, structure within the placenta [1,3]. Each villous trunk contains an artery and vein and such individual villi are termed “cotyledons”. Cotyledons are distributed uniformly over the placenta, forming the major subdivision of placental tissue. Larger cotyledons, the “anchoring villi”, extend through the placenta and penetrate the UPI to the interior layer of the uterus. At pregnancy near term, the uterus is a large, near-spherical muscular sac, 200–300 mm in diameter, 5.5–7.75 mm thick, surrounding the fetus and the placenta. The fetus is immersed in a bath of amniotic fluid that is in turn contained within a chorioamnion sac, extending as a mm-thick layer from the placenta and constrained by the interior of the uterus, Fig 1. During pregnancy, the viability of the fetus is critically dependent on the integrity and function of the UPI. In a normal birth process a complex series of biochemical signals alter and weaken the UPI and subsequent contractions of the uterus lead to detachment and release of the placenta from the uterus [1,18,27], giving rise to the (disposable) “afterbirth” [1]. However, prior to birth, a physical action may circumvent this process and force UPI mechanical failure and detachment of the placenta from the uterus, giving rise to placental abruption.

The basic mechanics of placental release and placental abruption are well established. In natural release at childbirth the uterus contracts in volume significantly [1], greatly reducing the area for placental attachment. As a consequence of “limited placental elasticity”, the placenta buckles away from the uterus as delamination takes place at the weakest layer of the UPI, “[like a] row of perforations between postage stamps”, leaving an adherent portion at the placental periphery. Sustained uterine contractions and tension applied to the umbilical cord by the birth attendant lead to eventual complete placental-uterine delamination of the UPI. Maternal trauma during pregnancy can lead to *abruptio placentae*, the premature separation of the UPI prior to birth. The most common cause of such trauma is blunt impact caused by motor vehicle collisions [6,7,28]. Sled test experiments and FEA-based models of such impacts show that the uterus is compressed along the direction of impact (primarily by the vehicle steering wheel) and extended perpendicular to that direction, leading to significant shear strain imposed on the UPI [12,23–25]. Such experiments and models

show correlations between impact velocities and resulting strains. When combined with the “real world” correlation between vehicle collision velocities and adverse fetal outcomes, the implication that placental abruption is caused by excess imposed shear leading to failure of the UPI is clear. Benirschke et al. [3] find that sudden detachment of one half or more of the placenta leads to fetal demise, consistent with the strong correlation noted by Ananth et al. [8] between the extent of placental abruption and stillbirth.

Although the fracture phenomena of placental detachment in both natural release (buckling) and forced abruption (shear strain) are well recognized, the mechanics of UPI failure have to date been considered in strength of materials approaches rather than a fundamental fracture approach. The prior approaches, particularly those applying FEA to trauma, focus on the strains generated in the tissues adjacent to the UPI. However, these approaches, often using sophisticated FEA models and output images, are indirect: It is the *strain energy* generated in the tissues and available for UPI fracture and delamination that controls placental release and abruption. Two energies per area, the mechanical energy release rate (derivable from the strains and strain energy) and the UPI fracture resistance (an interface property), together determine fracture behavior. An energy-based fracture mechanics framework using these parameters is developed here for description of natural placental release during childbirth and forced placental abruption as a consequence of trauma.

Background to the framework and context in terms of common structural materials is provided by consideration of the characteristic mechanical behavior and properties of the tissues involved. Tensile, compressive, and shear tests on placental tissue (with the vascular layer removed) indicate a material that displays moderately convex, strain-rate dependent, and hysteretic load-displacement behavior [29–35], typical of biological tissues. Characteristic tensile failure stresses and strains of such placental tissue are in the ranges 15–25 kPa and 0.35–0.55, respectively, although ranges for individual studies are typically greater than these. The characteristic secant modulus (stress/strain) at failure is thus about 45 kPa. Tests on whole placental specimens with the vascular layer intact show similar failure strains but significantly greater failure stresses, exceeding 150 kPa. Tensile tests on uterine tissue show a material that is considerably stiffer and stronger than placental tissues, but which also displays convex load-displacement behavior and considerable variability in failure parameters. Characteristic tensile failure stresses and strains are in the ranges 500–1500 kPa and 0.2–0.4, respectively, with characteristic secant moduli at failure of 100–1400 kPa [29, 36, 37]. In all cases reported, placental and uterine tissue failure was brittle—the mechanical response was elastic, with no indication of plastic deformation, prior to failure. In addition, the placental and uterine tissues did not exhibit the large strain nonlinear deformations characteristic of gels [38] or elastomers [39]—the responses were nearly linear. Biaxial and uniaxial tensile tests on chorioamniotic tissue also show a material that is stronger and stiffer than placental tissue, with a characteristic (brittle) strength of approximately 0.9 MPa (900 kPa) and elastic moduli in the range 2–5 MPa. [40, 41]. Similarly, uniaxial tensile tests on the constituents of the umbilical cord show materials that are stronger and stiffer than placental tissue, with characteristic strengths of approximately 1.5 MPa and moduli in the range 1–10 MPa [42]. At pregnancy near term, the amniotic fluid pressure is about 3 kPa above atmospheric pressure, such that thin- and thick-walled spherical pressure vessel approximations for the chorioamnion and uterus, respectively, lead to restraining tensile stresses in both of about 700 kPa [40, 43, 44]. From a functional point of view, the chorioamnion must remain intact during pregnancy and then rupture prior to birth, and the UPI must remain intact during pregnancy and then rupture after birth. Consideration of the above stress relative to the observed strengths suggests that the chorioamnion, and perhaps the uterus, are very close to failure immediately prior to birth, and the implications of this proximity have been considered earlier [40, 41, 44–48].

The next section builds on the mechanical properties and behaviors of tissues summarized here and develops a fracture mechanics model of forced UPI rupture prior to birth. The following section then uses the parameters developed and extends the fracture mechanics to model and predict UPI rupture after birth.

3 Fracture Mechanics of Abruption

3.1 Mechanical Energy Release Rate

Placental abruption is modeled here as an elastic disc, the placenta, bonded variably, partially abrupted, to a deformation-controlled substrate, the uterus, along the disc-substrate interface, the UPI. Schematic diagrams in section and plan view are shown in Fig 2. Prior to substrate deformation, the placental disc and uterine substrate are in quiescent, undeformed states and the disc is fully bonded to the substrate, Fig 2(A). On imposed extension of the substrate, the disc deforms and delaminates uniformly from the disc exterior toward the disc interior along the disc-substrate interface, so as to form an annular interface crack surrounding a central bonded area, Figs. 2(B)–(F). The analysis here of this geometry follows that of Thouless [49], using similar notation but different boundary conditions (the resulting outputs are compared below). The radius of the disc is R . The thickness of the disc is h . The radius of the bonded area is a ; a convenient geometrical factor is $\alpha = a/R$. The length of the interface crack or delamination is $c = R - a$. The relative areal extent of abruption is thus $1 - \alpha^2$. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the placental disc material are E and ν ; a convenient material factor is $\beta = (1 - \nu)/(1 + \nu)$.

The displacement, stress, strain, and elastic energy in the annulus of placental disc material parallel to the cracked area can be determined for various loading configurations using the thick-walled cylindrical vessel analysis. For radial coordinate r the radial displacement u is given by [50]

$$u = C_1 r + \frac{C_2}{r}. \quad (1)$$

The radial and circumferential strain components ε_r and ε_θ are given by

$$\varepsilon_r, \varepsilon_\theta = C_1 \mp \frac{C_2}{r^2}. \quad (2)$$

The radial and circumferential stress components σ_r and σ_θ are given by

$$\sigma_r, \sigma_\theta = E \left[\frac{C_1}{(1 - \nu)} \mp \frac{C_2}{r^2(1 + \nu)} \right]. \quad (3)$$

Deformation within the annulus is specified by the constants C_1 and C_2 determined by the loading and boundary conditions.

The process of abruption can be considered as the reaction of a disc initially bonded to a substrate as the substrate is placed under uniform equi-biaxial tensile strain, $\varepsilon_S > 0$. The initial deformed state, in which the placental disc is fully bonded to the strained uterine substrate and thus exhibits the same strain, is shown in Fig 2(B). The initial imposed radial displacement field u_S in the uniformly strained disc is

$$u_S = \varepsilon_S r, \quad (4)$$

such that the initial deformed position, r_S , of an element in the disc is

$$r_S = r + u_S = r(1 + \varepsilon_S), \quad (5)$$

where the subscript ‘‘S’’ indicates an initial condition determined by the substrate. The initial elastic strain energy density \tilde{U}_S (energy/volume) in the disc is uniform and is

$$\tilde{U}_S = \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1 - \nu)}, \quad (6)$$

such that the initial total elastic strain energy in the disc, U_S , is

$$U_S = \pi R^2 h \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1 - \nu)}, \quad (7)$$

where $\pi R^2 h$ is the volume of the disc.

The elastic strain energy in the placental disc is decreased if the disc exhibits annular delamination, leading to relaxation of the tensile strain and elastic energy density within the delaminated annulus. (The central region of the disc remains bonded to the strained substrate and there is no strain change in the substrate.) The resulting deformation in the delaminated annulus can be modeled by application of a stress free condition on the external boundary of the annulus and a displacement of the internal boundary of the annulus matched to that of the substrate. The change in elastic energy of the annulus on delamination, ΔU , is the difference between the elastic energy in the annulus with the specified boundary conditions and the initial elastic energy prior to delamination. Determination and interpretation of ΔU is a focus of the analysis. The boundary conditions are

$$\sigma_r|_{r=R} = 0 \quad (8)$$

and

$$u|_{r=a} = \varepsilon_S a. \quad (9)$$

The first boundary condition, Eq (8), gives, using Eq (3),

$$C_2 = C_1 R^2 / \beta \quad (10)$$

and the second, Eq (9), thus gives, using Eq (1),

$$C_1 = \varepsilon_S \alpha^2 \beta / (1 + \alpha^2 \beta), \quad (11)$$

from which C_2 and $u(r)$ follow directly. Note that the second boundary condition, Eq (9), is equivalent to imposing matched circumferential strains at the internal boundary, $\varepsilon_\theta|_{r=a} = \varepsilon_S$, and using Eq (2). The radial displacement within the annulus ($a \leq r \leq R$) is, *cf* Eq (4),

$$u = \varepsilon_S r \frac{\alpha^2 \beta}{1 + \alpha^2 \beta} (1 + R^2 / \beta r^2). \quad (12)$$

The relaxed position of an element in the annulus, r' , *cf* Eq (5), is thus

$$r' = r + u = r \left[1 + \varepsilon_S \frac{\alpha^2 \beta}{1 + \alpha^2 \beta} (1 + R^2 / \beta r^2) \right]. \quad (13)$$

Fig 3 is a plot of the radial position of elements in a placental disc as a function of the undeformed radial coordinate r . Three stages of delamination are shown and the parameters $R = 100$ mm, $\varepsilon_S = 0.4$, $\alpha = 0.5$, and $\nu = 0.33$ (such that $\beta = 0.5$) were used, typical of placental abruption. The lower fine line shows the position in the undeformed quiescent state, $r_0 = r$, labeled 0. The dashed line shows the position in the initial deformed state, r_S , Eq (5), labeled S. The upper bold line shows the position in the relaxed state after delamination or abruption, r' , Eq (13), labeled A. The bonded central region is indicated shaded. Within this region the final position is given by r_S . Exterior to this region in the delaminated annulus, however, the final position recovers toward the undeformed quiescent state, as indicated by the arrow. As shown in the schematic diagrams of Fig 2(C)–(E), this recovery increases as the delamination increases.

The stresses and strains within the annulus are

$$\sigma_r, \sigma_\theta = \frac{E\varepsilon_S}{(1-\nu)} \frac{\alpha^2\beta}{1+\alpha^2\beta} (1 \mp R^2/r^2) \quad (14)$$

and

$$\varepsilon_r, \varepsilon_\theta = \varepsilon_S \frac{\alpha^2\beta}{1+\alpha^2\beta} (1 \mp R^2/\beta r^2). \quad (15)$$

The radial dependence of the elastic strain energy density $\tilde{U}(r)$ is thus

$$\tilde{U}(r) = \frac{\sigma_r \varepsilon_r}{2} + \frac{\sigma_\theta \varepsilon_\theta}{2} = \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{\alpha^2\beta}{(1+\alpha^2\beta)} \right]^2 (1 + R^4/\beta r^4), \quad (16)$$

The ratio of the local strain energy density in the relaxed annulus, Eq (16), to the initial strain energy density, Eq (6), is thus

$$\frac{\tilde{U}(r)}{\tilde{U}_S} = \left[\frac{\alpha^2\beta}{(1+\alpha^2\beta)} \right]^2 (1 + R^4/\beta r^4). \quad (17)$$

If the undeformed coordinate r is taken as a parameter, Eqs. (13) and (17) form a parametric set for the variation of the relative strain energy density in the deformed disc. This variation is shown in Fig 4 as a plot of the relative elastic strain energy density $\tilde{U}(r)/\tilde{U}_S$ as a function of the deformed coordinate r' . The placental abruption parameters given above were used and, as in Fig 3, the bonded central region is indicated shaded and the dashed line shows the initial external position $r_S(R)$. Recovery in position of the delaminated annulus is most easily recognized by noting that at the periphery $r'(R) < r_S(R)$, as indicated by the arrow. The solid line shows that the relative strain energy density within the delaminated annulus relaxes from the internal bonded region toward the radial traction free external perimeter of the disc. As shown in the schematic diagrams of Fig 2(C)–(E), this relaxation increases in intensity as the delamination increases.

Using Eq (16) the elastic strain energy U in the relaxed annulus is

$$U = \int_a^R \tilde{U}(r) 2\pi r h dr = \frac{\pi R^2 h \varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{\alpha^2\beta(1-\alpha^2)}{1+\alpha^2\beta} \right], \quad (18)$$

given by an integral rather than a product, Eq (7). The initial elastic strain energy in the annulus, U_α , following Eq (7), is

$$U_\alpha = \pi R^2 h \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1-\nu)} (1-\alpha^2) \quad (19)$$

such that the change in energy ΔU noted above is

$$\Delta U = U - U_\alpha = -\pi R^2 h \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{1-\alpha^2}{1+\alpha^2\beta} \right] \quad (20)$$

and it is observed that $\Delta U < 0$: delamination decreases the strain energy in the strained disc, or, abruption decreases the strain energy in the stretched placenta. The area of the cracked region is $A = \pi R^2 - \pi a^2 = \pi R^2(1 - \alpha^2)$. The fracture system, substrate and disc, is loaded by a “fixed grips” condition as strain ε_S is imposed on the substrate. As a consequence, the mechanical energy release rate, J , for crack extension (increasing A , decreasing α) is $J = -d\Delta U/dA$ [51] (using J to indicate a mechanical energy release rate in a potentially nonlinear material). Thus, using Eq (20) and noting that $dA = \pi R^2(-2\alpha d\alpha)$,

$$J = \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E h}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{\beta+1}{(1+\alpha^2\beta)^2} \right]. \quad (21)$$

The linear dimension of the crack, the annulus width, is given by

$$c = R(1 - \alpha). \quad (22)$$

Equations (21) and (22) form a parametric set in α for $J(c)$. It is clear that as both J and c increase as α decreases, that $J(c)$ is an increasing function. In addition, as placental abruption is a *biaxial* deformation and fracture phenomenon, the crack driving force J depends significantly on the coupling between the radial and circumferential strains in the biaxial field as characterized by ν and $\beta(\nu)$. Fig 5 shows plots of $J(c)$ for a range of ν values and the placental parameters given above, using $E = 45$ kPa and $h = 10$ mm. The J values are somewhat greater, about 100 J m^{-2} , than those usually encountered for brittle ceramics, usually about 10 J m^{-2} [51, 52], reflecting the greater strains and dimensions involved here, notwithstanding the diminished elastic modulus. As anticipated, $J(c)$ is an increasing function with significant ν dependence. $J(c)$ is a configurational force, acting to drive crack extension.

In comparison with the above analysis, Thouless [49] considered the loading of a disc under initial biaxial tensile stress bonded to a rigid substrate. The disc exhibited annular delamination leading to relaxation of the tensile stress within the annulus and the central region of the disc remained fixed and bonded to the rigid substrate. The deformation in the delaminating annulus was modeled by application of a compressive stress on the external boundary of the annulus equal and opposite to the initial tension, so as to render the external boundary stress free. As the internal boundary remained fixed to the rigid substrate, the elastic strain energy in the annulus generated by application of the compressive stress was taken as the negative of the change in elastic energy of the annulus on delamination and relaxation. The boundary conditions and frame of reference used by Thouless were thus both reversed relative to those used here, such that the resultant $J(c)$ function was identical to Eq (21).

3.2 Fracture Resistance and Abrupted Area

The configurational force acting to oppose crack extension is the fracture resistance, Γ , the energy per area required to create a fracture surface [51, 52]. Equilibrium generally is given by balanced forces and for a fracture system equilibrium is given by the balance of crack driving and crack resistance forces. These configurational forces are the mechanical energy release rate J and the fracture resistance Γ , such that fracture equilibrium is given by the equality $J = \Gamma$. As noted above $J = J(c)$ and in general fracture

resistance is also crack length dependent, $\Gamma = \Gamma(c)$. Stability of a fracture system is determined by the relative magnitudes of dJ/dc and $d\Gamma/dc$. A fracture system is stable for $d\Gamma/dc > dJ/dc$. An important aspect of Eq (21) and Fig 5 is that $J(c)$ is destabilizing, as $dJ/dc > 0$. As a consequence, equilibrium stability of a placental abruption fracture system requires that $\Gamma(c)$ must be a steeply increasing function, at least over the domain of relevant crack lengths. Equilibrium stability in this context means that the UPI delamination extends to a fixed stable length, $c < R$, or fixed relative abrupted area, $(1 - \alpha^2) < 1$, (or fixed bonded area $\alpha^2 > 0$) for a prescribed uterus strain and does not delaminate the entire UPI ($\alpha^2 = 0$). A $\Gamma(c)$ variation is now considered that leads to stable UPI delamination. The variation has simple physical interpretation in terms of UPI structure, provides insight into the conditions for both no abruption and complete abruption, and is consistent with natural placental release during birth (next section).

Fig 6(A) shows the schematic view of the delaminated placental disc from Fig 2(E) and a magnified view of the delamination tip. To the right of the delamination on the intact UPI, discrete branched entities are shown. In highly schematized form these entities represent cotyledons comprising terminal villi from the fetal capillary system penetrating the uterine decidua [1–4, 16]. Such cotyledons are typically uniformly distributed over the UPI. Furtherest to the left, on the delaminated UPI, the cotyledon is completely removed from the uterine surface. Between these two extremes, the cotyledons are extended and sheared and impart bridging tractions that oppose delamination opening and extension. It is also likely that maternal spiral arteries generate a similar array of bridging tractions, extending in the opposite direction from uterus to placenta. Such bridging arrays are characterized by a distance δ describing the spatial extent of the array and a line force (force/length) f describing the restraining effect of the array along the crack front, Fig 6(B) [52]. For short cracks or delaminations, $c < \delta$, the fracture resistance is determined solely by the interfacial fracture resistance in the absence of bridging, Γ_0 . For longer cracks, $c > \delta$, the bridging zone impedes crack extension, initially increasing with crack length before tending to an upper value associated with steady-state zone progression. The variation of fracture resistance with crack length (for circular cracks) is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(c) &= \Gamma_0 & c < \delta \\ &= \Gamma_0 \left[1 + B \left(1 - \delta^{3/2}/c^{3/2} \right) \right]^2 & c \geq \delta \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$B = (f^2/\Gamma_0 E \delta)^{1/2} \approx 1$ is a dimensionless term characterizing the relative effects of bridging and $\Gamma \rightarrow (1 + B)^2 \Gamma_0$ for $c \gg \delta$. Many other formulations are possible, including those that take the constitutive behavior of the bridges into account [52], but Eq (23) describes increasing fracture resistance phenomena without over-parameterizing.

Fig 7 shows a plot of $\Gamma(c)$ using $\Gamma_0 = 50 \text{ J m}^{-2}$, $\delta = 31 \text{ mm}$, and $B = 1.15$. The first value is typical for immiscible polymer-polymer interfaces [53, 54], the second value is consistent with placental and cotyledon geometry [1, 3], and the third value gives a lower bound interfacial stress exerted by the bridging elements, $f/\delta \approx 0.6 \text{ MPa}$, consistent with the greater monolithic placental and uterine strengths noted above. The values of Γ_0 and δ are indicated in Fig 7. Fig 8 shows plots of $J(c)$ using Eq 21, the placental values above, and uterine strain values of 0.36, 0.40, and 0.42; the central curves of Figs. 5 and 8 are identical. The $J(c)$ curves are overlaid on the plot of $\Gamma(c)$ from Fig 7 and the equilibrium points of intersection, $J(c) = \Gamma(c)$, are indicated by gray dots. The equilibria are stable as $d\Gamma/dc > dJ/dc$ at each intersection. The interpretation of Fig 8 is that a stable placental delamination of $c = 50 \text{ mm}$ (in undeformed coordinates, Fig 3) is generated by an imposed uterine strain of $\varepsilon_S = 0.4$. Greater and lesser strains generate larger and smaller delaminations

or abruptions, respectively.

The complete set of stable equilibrium points obtained from plots such as Fig 8 provides a response curve for extent of placental abruption as a function of imposed uterine strain. Equating Eq (21) and Eq (23) and using Eq (22) gives the required functional relationship, $\alpha = \alpha(\varepsilon_S)$, noting that the relative area of placental abruption is $(1 - \alpha^2)$. Fig 9 plots this quantity as a function of imposed uterine strain as a solid line, using the parameters given above. Consideration of Fig 8 shows that there is a limited domain of imposed strain that give rise to stable abruption dimensions. For strains less than a lower bound, the equilibrium criterion is not met, $J < \Gamma_0$. This bound is indicated by the vertical dashed line in Fig 9, approximately $\varepsilon_S < 0.27$. For strains greater than an upper bound, the equality $J = \Gamma_0$ occurs for complete abruption, $\alpha = 0$. This bound is indicated by the shaded region in Fig 9, approximately $\varepsilon_S > 0.43$. The solid line extends between the two bounds and indicates that stable partial placental abruption is possible, although extremely sensitive to uterine strain. For minor uterine strain, no abruption is predicted. For most imposed uterine strains, complete abruption is predicted. The response curve can be compared with FEA-based simulations that are adapted by experimental observations. The solid symbols in Fig 9 show the results of [23] for the risk of adverse fetal outcome as a function of calculated uterine strain (using motor vehicle velocity as a parameter). The domain of increase is broader than that observed here but median damage strain, about 0.4, is similar. The upper open symbol in Fig 9 shows the result cited by [29] for complete placental abruption, in agreement with the assessment here. The lower open symbols in Fig 9 show the uterine strain criterion used by [24] for the onset of fetal damage in FEA simulations. The criterion is similar to the lower bound for stable abruption observed here. As both the analytical abruption fracture model and the FEA abruption simulations [23, 24, 29] are adapted to similar observations, the predicted responses from both are similar.

The next section builds on the fracture mechanics framework developed here and applies the framework to model and predict physiological UPI rupture and placental release after birth. In particular, the physiological rupture model uses the same fracture resistance variation used to describe placental abruption. Predictions of the physiological model are thus a test of the overall fracture approach.

4 Fracture Mechanics of Physiological Release

The fracture mechanics of natural placental release exhibits similarities to, and differences from, that assumed for placental abruption. In both cases the placenta is modeled as an elastic disc bonded to a deformation-controlled substrate, the uterus, along the disc-substrate interface, the UPI. Schematic diagrams in section and plan view are shown in Fig 10. Prior to substrate deformation, the placental disc and uterine substrate are in quiescent, undeformed states and the disc is fully bonded to the substrate, Fig 10(A). In the natural release process there is a *contraction* of the uterine substrate, leading to a compressive strain, $\varepsilon_S < 0$, imposed in the placental disc, distinct from uterine tension in the abruption process. In reaction to the imposed compressive strain the disc buckles at a delamination at the disc interior, with displacement primarily normal to the substrate. The delamination propagates a crack toward the disc exterior along the disc-substrate interface, so as to form a circular interface crack surrounded by an external bonded area, Figs. 10(B)–(F). In contrast, in the abruption process delamination occurs in an annulus at the disc exterior with displacement consisting primarily of in-plane shear. The abruption propagates toward the disc interior so as to form an annular interface crack surrounding a bonded interior. In both cases, however, fracture and deformation relaxes elastic strain energy that was generated in the placental disc by the imposed uterine strain.

The buckling analysis here is based on that of Hutchinson et al. [55]. As above, the radius and thickness of the disc are R and h and the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the disc material are E and ν . The expressions for the initial elastic strain energy density \tilde{U}_S and elastic strain energy U_S in the compressively deformed disc are identical to those for the tensile placental disc, Eqs. (6) and (7), noting that the expressions are quadratic in strain. The radius of the delaminated and buckled region is c . As in consideration of abruption, attention here is focused on stable equilibrium fracture.

The starting point in analysis is to assume that in the quiescent state a weakened or delaminated region of radius $c > h$ exists on the UPI in the center of the placental disc, usually located beneath the umbilical cord attachment point [1]. Buckling of the placental disc at this delamination occurs for compressive uterine substrate strains imposed on the disc of magnitude greater than a critical value ε_C given by

$$\varepsilon_C = \frac{1.22}{(1 + \nu)} \left(\frac{h}{c} \right)^2. \quad (24)$$

For substrate strains of magnitude ε_S greater than ε_C , the buckle height δ is given by

$$\delta \approx b_1 h \left(\frac{\varepsilon_S}{\varepsilon_C} - 1 \right)^{1/2}, \quad (25)$$

where $b_1 = b_1(\nu) \approx 0.7$ is a function of Poisson's ratio. Equation (25) is somewhat analogous to Eq (12).

The mechanical energy release rate J acting on the crack formed at the buckle is given by

$$J = b_2 \tilde{U}_S h \left[1 - \left(\frac{\varepsilon_C}{\varepsilon_S} \right)^x \right], \quad (26)$$

where $b_2 = b_2(\nu)$. In the asymptotic limit $\varepsilon_S \rightarrow \varepsilon_C$, $b_2 = 1/[1 + 0.90(1 - \nu)]$ and $x = 2$ [55]. An empirical fit to the full numerical result gives $b_2 = 1/[1 + 0.25(1 - \nu)]$ and $x = 1.15$ and these are the parameters used here. Equations (24) and (26) can be combined to give $J_\infty(c)$ appropriate to a circular buckle in an infinite film on substrate system, as used by Hutchinson et al. [55]. For the finite placental disc on uterine substrate system here a boundary condition must be imposed such that the mechanical energy release rate at complete delamination is limited to the total energy per area of the initial bonded disc. The boundary condition is

$$J|_{c=R} = \tilde{U}_S h = \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E h}{(1 - \nu)}. \quad (27)$$

Solving for $J(c)$ with the boundary condition gives

$$J(c) = \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E h}{(1 - \nu)} \left\{ 1 + b_2 \left[\frac{1.22 h^2}{(1 + \nu) R^2 \varepsilon_S} \right]^x \left[1 - \left(\frac{R}{c} \right)^{2x} \right] \right\}. \quad (28)$$

For $c \ll R$, $J_\infty(c)$ is recovered. For $c = R$, the limit of Eq (27) is reached. $J(c)$ exhibits some similarities with Eq (21): The first, amplitude, term is identical, reflecting the total energy per area in the initial bonded disc and the second, crack length, term includes Poisson's ratio and finite size dependences. Fig 11 shows plots of $J(c)$ from Eq (28) for a range of ν values and the placental parameters given above, using $\varepsilon_S = 0.4$ and $h = 10$ mm. $J(c)$ is an increasing function with significant ν dependence that exhibits two major differences from the variations characterizing abruption in Fig 5. The $J(c)$ function increases from 0 at a crack length slightly larger than the placental disc thickness (rather than 0 crack length) and approaches an

asymptotic value at crack lengths of about 2–3 placental disc thickness, thereby exhibiting a destabilizing to neutral transition.

Fig 12 shows plots of $J(c)$ using Eq 28, the placental values above, and uterine strain values of -0.35 , -0.45 , and -0.50 . The $J(c)$ curves are overlaid on the plot of $\Gamma(c)$ from Fig 7 and the equilibrium points of intersection, $J(c) = \Gamma(c)$, are indicated by gray dots. The equilibria are stable as $d\Gamma/dc > dJ/dc$ at each intersection. The interpretation of Fig 12 is that a stable placental delamination of about $c = 50$ mm (in undeformed coordinates) is generated by an imposed uterine strain of $\varepsilon_S = -0.45$. Greater and lesser strain magnitudes generate larger and smaller equilibrium release delaminations, respectively. Fig 12 provides an explanation of why continued contraction is often required to generate placental release during labor [1]. The placental delaminations in Fig 12 are stable for a fixed level of imposed uterine compressive strain, Figs. 10(c)–(e), such that increased compression or additional force (usually a central tensile force applied through the umbilical cord) is required to cause complete delamination.

5 Nonlinear Deformation Perturbation

Although nonlinear effects in the deformation responses of placental tissue are small it is important to consider nonlinear perturbations to the fracture analyses. The scale of nonlinear effects can be assessed by noting that the deformation domain of the tissue is bounded by the failure stress and strain $(\sigma_f, \varepsilon_f)$ and convenient normalized variables are $x = \varepsilon/\varepsilon_f$ and $y = \sigma/\sigma_f$. In common with other biological tissues (chorioamnion [40, 45, 46], uterus [36, 37], umbilical cord [42], and tendons and ligaments [56]), the predominant behavior within the deformation domain, particularly for large deformations, $0.25 \leq (x, y) \leq 1$, is linear. The linear region is displaced from the deformation origin by a small nonlinear region, $0 \leq (x, y) \leq 0.25$, giving the entire response a nonlinear appearance. A simple arithmetic expression that describes observed behavior, in which the scale of nonlinear effects is explicit, is

$$y = x - a[1 - (2x - 1)^2], \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (29)$$

where a is the amplitude of the nonlinear perturbation. In these coordinates the secant modulus of the unperturbed material is 1. For placental tissue the amplitude of the negative perturbation is ≈ 0.2 . The elastic strain energy density in deformed nonlinear tissue varies as

$$\bar{U} \sim \int y dx \quad (30)$$

and hence it is clear that the negative nonlinear perturbation decreases the strain energy density from the linear basis, particularly at small strains.

The physical consequence of the nonlinear effects encapsulated in Eqs. (29) and (30) is that the strain energy density in the delaminated placenta is inhomogeneously depressed, as the deformation field is inhomogeneous. On abruption at the delaminated placental periphery normal tractions vanish and hence the strain energy density is substantially depressed. At the bonded placental center strain continuity is maintained and the strain energy density is only weakly suppressed. The arithmetic consequence is that the spatial variation in strain energy density within the delaminated placenta is greater for a nonlinear material. An expression

for this variation on axisymmetric delamination is perturbation of Eq (16):

$$\bar{U}(r) = \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{\alpha^2 \beta}{(1+\alpha^2 \beta)} \right]^2 \left[1 + \frac{R^{4+p}}{\beta r^{4+p}} \right], \quad (31)$$

where p is a small value. It is recognized that the effective modulus E and Poisson's ratio factor β of the material are weakly strain dependent, but this does not affect the spatial variation described by r . After some manipulation, completing the integral of Eq (18) and the subtraction of Eq (20), to leading order in p , the change in energy of the delaminated nonlinearly deforming placenta is

$$\Delta U = -(1-p)\pi R^2 h \frac{\varepsilon_S^2 E}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{1-\alpha^2}{1+\alpha^2 \beta} \right], \quad (32)$$

which differs from Eq (20) by only a factor of $(1-p)$. As a consequence, the mechanical energy release rate is given by

$$J = \frac{(1-p)\varepsilon_S^2 E h}{(1-\nu)} \left[\frac{\beta+1}{(1+\alpha^2 \beta)^2} \right], \quad (33)$$

with the same functional dependence as Eq (21) and amplitude depressed by a factor of $(1-p)$. The second equation in the parametric set, Eq (22), remains unchanged. There are two ways to interpret the above equation with reference to Fig 8. First, to take all system parameters as given and recognize that the material non-linearity decreases J such that the equilibrium crack lengths are reduced. As $p \approx a$, this interpretation suggests stable equilibrium crack lengths about 20 % shorter than those indicated. Second, to take the crack lengths as given and recognize that the strain or elastic modulus should be re-estimated. This interpretation suggests that the strains used should be approximately 10% greater, for example, or moduli 20 % greater. Observations of placental abruption indicate relative crack lengths in the range 30–90 % and estimations of mechanical properties have relative uncertainties of approximately $\pm 25\%$. Hence, non-linear deformation effects, although probably present, do not significantly perturb the fracture analysis and are not significant relative to current experimental uncertainties. A similar assessment can be made for the natural release buckling analysis.

In early work considering fracture in non-linear materials, Sih and MacDonald [57] arrived at similar relations to those here: to leading order for small perturbations from linearity the strain energy is modulated by an amplitude factor, and hence so is the mechanical energy release rate, Eqs. (32) and (33). For larger perturbations, the crack length dependence is also altered (here $\alpha^2 \rightarrow \alpha^{2(1-p)}$, which slightly destabilizes the system). However, it is important to recognize that the above arithmetic considerations do not change the underlying physics of placental abruption and release (or the cantilevers considered by Sih and MacDonald): these processes are based on the fracture phenomena of work converted into elastic energy converted into surface energy (Sih and MacDonald also considered kinetic energy). Nonlinear behavior is simply an arithmetic perturbation of the physical description. In this case, a linear analysis was both appropriate to the materials under consideration and enabled the energy conversions noted above to be detailed clearly. The linear analysis was based on experimental observations and was both descriptive and predictive. However, all energy-based fracture analyses integrate over material constitutive responses and thus are not too sensitive to non-linear details, as shown in the above perturbation analysis. Linear elastic fracture mechanics of course requires material linearity, but this was not invoked in the energy-based approaches here or by Sih and MacDonald [57].

6 Discussion and Conclusions

The analyses here have developed the essential physics and fracture mechanics to describe delamination of the human placenta from the maternal uterus during both accidental trauma and physiological childbirth. Both delamination processes, along the uterine-placental interface (UPI), are driven by displacements imposed on the placenta by the uterus: In natural placental release, delamination is caused by compressive uterine contractions arising internally. In forced placental abruption, delamination is caused by tensile uterine extensions arising externally. In both cases, delamination and fracture of the UPI is a consequence of the transformation of elastic strain energy in the placenta into surface energy on the UPI. In natural release, relaxation of elastic strain energy in the placenta is associated with out of plane buckling displacement, as described earlier by Cunningham et al. [1]. In forced abruption, relaxation of elastic strain energy in the placenta is associated with in plane shear displacement, as surmised earlier by Rupp et al. [29]. The analyses are in qualitative and quantitative agreement with published component structures and dimensions, materials properties (elastic moduli, strengths, interfacial energies), and phenomena (imposed strains, resultant crack lengths). A key feature of the analyses is extension of the base fracture mechanics models [49, 55] to include increasing fracture resistance of the UPI arising from interfacial bridging [52]. A single UPI fracture resistance variation described stable equilibrium delaminations in both release and abruption.

Perhaps the most striking new result from the present fracture analysis is that stable partial abruption is expected for some traumatic placental events. The example of Fig 9 shows that for strains imposed by the uterus between lower and upper bounds of approximately 25 % and 45 % stable equilibrium delaminations are predicted, increasing from approximately 10 % of placental area to complete 100 % abruption. This is very different from a strength of materials approach that implies nonspecific “abruption” once a lower bound threshold strain is surpassed. Here, the onset of abruption is expressed in terms characterizing equilibrium fracture of the UPI rather than a critical strain characterizing failure of adjacent placental or uterine tissue. In addition to describing the failure mechanism explicitly, the fracture analysis provides quantitative predictions of the stable post-threshold behavior. The predicted stable partial abruption probably also explains the correlation between fetal mortality, vehicle crash velocity, and FEA modeled uterine strain noted by Auriault et al. [24], also plotted in Fig 9. Stable partial delamination of the placenta from the uterus is of course well known in natural release during childbirth [1]. The fracture analyses here make clear that such delaminations differ in the signs of the imposed strain—negative for release, positive for abruption—with consequent differences in geometry—out of plane buckling of the placental center during natural release, in plane shear of the placental periphery during abruption. In quantitative detail, natural physiological release of the placenta at childbirth requires compressive uterine strains of at least -50% . Forced abruption associated with trauma requires tensile uterine strains of approximately 35 % to generate the 50 % placental abruption associated with fetal mortality [3].

The mechanics models for release and abruption have several common features that can be refined to more closely represent the delamination processes. First, a more realistic boundary condition for the deformed uterus is an imposed far-field displacement rather than an imposed global strain. Such a boundary condition must be coupled with elastic relaxation of the uterus as buckling or shear delamination of the placenta proceeds. Second, both the uterus and the placenta exhibit non-linear convex elastic responses. Such responses could be incorporated into the dual uterine and placental relaxations. However, as noted above energy-based approaches to fracture “integrate” over these details and scalar measurements of crack area are insensitive to such effects. For example, substrate compliance is simply accommodated by an increased effective overlayer thickness, and non-linear elasticity is simply accommodated by use of the secant

modulus, which averages over a stress-strain response. Deformation rate dependence is similarly handled by such averaging and the secant modulus was used in a recent review of female reproductive tissues to compare overall mechanical responses [58]. Third, the uterus, placenta, and UPI are all curved, and the placenta is of variable thickness. From an energy perspective, these geometrical issues can be addressed by modifications to the integral of Eq (18) and the derivative leading to Eq (21). Fourth, the $J(c)$ functions developed here are both strictly mid-domain intermediate crack length asymptotes, applicable for $h \ll c \ll R$. For descriptions of release and abruption as stable equilibrium mid-domain fractures, these functions are appropriate. Description of fracture initiation however, particularly at placental edges on abruption, requires $J(c)$ functions that describe behavior at short crack lengths, $c < h$, that can describe unstable behavior. Thouless [49] develops and shows the linear, $J \sim c$, asymptotic variations and overlayer thickness dependence for such short cracks (and also, of less interest here, for long cracks, $c \rightarrow R$). The short and intermediate $J(c)$ functions could be combined to provide a more complete description of behavior.

A feature of the refinements mentioned above—to boundary conditions, component and crack geometries, and material constitutive laws—is that the complexity and number of parameters in mathematical description of the phenomena increases. However, the underlying physics—conversion of elastic energy into surface energy—remains unchanged (e.g. Sih and MacDonald [57]). A better approach to modelling placental release and abruption might thus be to implement FEA-based models of the elastic energy changes on fracture. For example, replacing Eqs. (1)–(20) describing abruption with numerical FEA calculations of strain energy. The trade-off is that clear insight into the effects of various parameters is lost but better representation of components and materials is gained (e.g. Auriault et al [24] use a nonlinear multiparameter Ogden model of placental deformation within a multicomponent vehicle model). There are two aspects to be considered in modelling UPI fracture with FEA-based approaches. The first aspect is that fracture is an energy-based phenomenon. Thus, traditional FEA model outputs that focus on the forces and displacements and consequent stresses and strains developed on loading a system [23, 24, 29] do not usually provide sufficient information for considerations of fracture. Implicit fracture simulations can be performed using such analyses, however, by evaluating elastic strain energy changes from the stresses and strains calculated in static fracture systems. Explicit fracture simulations require more specialized analyses that implement special crack tip elements and global and local fracture criteria in dynamic fracture systems [60]. The second aspect is that experimental approaches in this area are necessarily limited. Experimental measurements of material properties are possible (e.g. [30, 31, 37, 59]), although techniques beyond simple tensile tests and acoustic velocity measurements are required to evaluate full non-linear and time-dependent deformation and fracture behaviors. Mechanical tests such as biaxial loading, cyclic loading, and stress relaxation [40, 45, 46] are required. Experimental measurements of component geometries, using tomographic techniques in three dimensions, are also possible [26]. Evaluations of phenomena, especially the extent of UPI delamination, can be quantified by ultrasonic techniques [59, 61] during natural release at birth [1], after forced abruption as a consequence of trauma [7], or after insufficient uterine contraction leading to hemorrhage after placental detachment [10]. However, these are the full scope of measurements and assessments. The implication is that progress in understanding the effects of placental and UPI mechanical behavior on maternal and fetal health [16] is dependent on FEA-based models. A similar conclusion lead to the development of FEA-based models and microfluidic-based studies of biochemical behavior of placental- and UPI-related phenomena [19–22], and more recently to FEA-based consideration of uterine rupture [17].

The considerations here of UPI fracture during mammalian birth are part of a broader view: In physiological contexts fracture phenomena are largely restricted to, and necessary for, reproduction. This view

encompasses both plants and animals: Fracture behavior is characterized by a decrease in a fracture resistance and an increase in a crack driving force leading to unstable fracture. In plants, seed dormancy is terminated by fracture of the seed coat, leading to plant germination. Water absorption by the seed through the porous coat leads to seed expansion and tensile stress in the coat. Combined with mechanical and chemical degradation of the coat by surrounding wet soil particles, fracture is the eventual outcome [62, 63]. In many shark species, embryo development occurs within a leathery egg case. On exposure to salt water after expulsion from the maternal shark the shell develops splits such that at the conclusion of embryo development the juvenile shark can rupture the egg case and emerge [64–66]. In birds, embryo development occurs within a stiff, brittle, mineralized egg shell [67]. Embryonic development of the chick is enabled by removal of minerals from the shell to form the chick skeleton, thereby simultaneously weakening the shell and strengthening the chick [68]. At the conclusion of embryonic development the chick fractures the egg shell from within and emerges. In humans, embryo development occurs within a pressurized fluid-filled compliant elastic sac, the chorioamnion membrane. During gestation and embryo development, pressure in the sac increases and the sac material weakens, leading to unstable fracture of the membrane as part of the birth process [40, 41, 45–48]. Another aspect of the birth process, the release of the placenta by rupture of the UPI was a focus of the work here. In all the examples considered, fracture is not a pathological event but a necessary and natural part of reproduction.

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Competing Interests

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Nomenclature

A	area of cracked region, mm ²
a	radius of bonded region, mm
B	relative bridging amplitude; $(f^2/\Gamma_0 E\delta)^{1/2}$
b_1	geometry constant
b_2	geometry constant
C_1	displacement function constant
C_2	displacement function constant, m ²
c	crack length, mm
E	Young's modulus, kPa
f	bridging restraint line force, N m ⁻¹
h	thickness of disc (placenta), mm
J	mechanical energy release rate, J m ⁻²
R	radius of disc (placenta), mm
r	radial coordinate, mm
U	elastic strain energy, J
\tilde{U}	elastic strain energy density, energy/volume, J m ⁻³ ; U/V
u	displacement, mm
V	volume of disc (placenta), m ³
α	relative radius of bonded region; a/R
β	material elastic factor; $(1 - \nu)(1 + \nu)$
Γ	fracture resistance, J m ⁻²
ΔU	change in energy, J
δ	bridging distance, mm
ε	strain
ν	Poisson's ratio
σ	stress, kPa
θ	circumferential coordinate

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Fig 1. Schematic diagram of a human pregnancy. The major mechanical components considered here are identified. Maternal anterior shown to left. Fracture and delamination of the uterine-placental interface (UPI) is the focus of this work.

Fig 2. Schematic diagrams of placental abruption. The process is modeled as a disc on substrate delamination process; (A)–(E) sections, (F) plan. (A) Quiescent undeformed state. (B) Initial deformed state arising from imposed substrate tensile strain. The vertical dotted lines indicate the initial extent of the deformed disc. (C)–(E) Increasing delamination of the disc-substrate interface and strain relaxation of the disc at the external boundary. (F) Plane view of (E).

Fig 3. Plot of positions of placental disc elements. Quiescent state (0, fine line), initial deformed state on imposed substrate strain (S, dashed line), and relaxed state on abruption (A, bold line). Central bonded region shown shaded, relaxation indicated by arrow.

Fig 4. Plot of relative elastic strain energy density. Deformed coordinates used for relaxed placental disc elements. Central bonded region is shown shaded, initial deformed disc radius is indicated by dashed line, relaxation of disc exterior indicated by arrow. The elastic strain energy density decreases markedly in the delaminated region between the bonded interior and the radial traction free exterior.

Fig 5. Plots of mechanical energy release rate. Variations are shown as functions of crack length, $J(c)$, for placental abruption, noting the effects of Poisson's ratio ν . $J(c)$ is an increasing function over the crack length domain, indicating that J is a destabilizing crack driving force.

Fig 6. Diagrams of restraining bridging at the uterine-placental interface (UPI). [Delamination following Fig 2(E).] (A) Schematic diagram of capillaries in the form of terminal villi in cotyledon clusters bridging the delaminating UPI. The cotyledons extend as the delamination crack opens right to left. (B) Diagram of the fracture mechanics components used to model bridging effects: a compressive line force, magnitude f , imposed a characteristic distance δ behind the crack tip.

Fig 7. Plot of fracture resistance. Variation shown as a function of crack length, $\Gamma(c)$, for placental abruption, noting the base interfacial fracture resistance Γ_0 and the characteristic length scale δ for fracture resistance increase associated with bridging. $\Gamma(c)$ is an increasing function over the crack length domain, indicating that that Γ is a stabilizing crack resistance force.

Fig 8. Plots of mechanical energy release rate. Variations are shown as functions of crack length, $J(c)$, for different levels of imposed uterine strain ϵ indicated and fracture resistance $\Gamma(c)$ of the UPI. Stable equilibrium placental abruption configurations are indicated by the gray dots. An imposed uterine strain of 0.4 leads to a 50 mm abruption crack.

Fig 9. Plot of relative area of placental abruption. Variation is shown as a function of imposed uterine strain predicted from the fracture mechanics-based model: Dashed line, threshold strain for stable abruption; shaded area, complete abruption; solid line, partial abruption that increases with intermediate strain. Solid symbols represent FEA-based partial abruption projections. Open symbols represent FEA-based threshold and complete abruption estimates.

Fig 10. Schematic diagrams of placental release. The process is modeled as a disc on substrate delamination process; (A)–(E) sections, (F) plan. (A) Quiescent undeformed state. (B) Initial deformed state arising from imposed substrate compressive strain. The vertical dotted lines indicate the initial extent of the deformed disc. (C)–(E) Increasing delamination of the disc-substrate interface and buckling of the disc at the center. (F) Plane view of (E).

Fig 11. Plots of mechanical energy release rate. Variations are shown as functions of crack length, $J(c)$, for placental release, noting the effects of Poisson's ratio ν . $J(c)$ is initially an increasing function over the crack length domain before tending to an invariant value, indicating that J is initially a destabilizing crack driving force before becoming neutral.

Fig 12. Plots of mechanical energy release rate. Variations are shown as functions of crack length, $J(c)$, for different levels of imposed uterine contraction strain ε indicated and fracture resistance $\Gamma(c)$ of the UPI. Stable equilibrium placental release configurations are indicated by the gray dots. An imposed uterine strain of 0.45 leads to an approximately 50 mm release crack.